

EVERYTHING THAT YOU DON'T KNOW

ABOUT VARICOSE VEINS

Varicose veins are not something new that has evolved a few years back but present here for a very long time and everything which is common and old has some bogus revolving around. In this article, you will learn facts about veins and varicose vein treatment available. These myths involve:

Varicose Veins happens to those who are old

This is untrue as told by the veins center la Jolla there are some people who got this problem at a very young age and they were perfectly normal. One of the significant factors that ailment the condition is genetics. Research studies done by the [veins centers la Jolla](#) revealed a 50% chance of catching the condition if any of your close relatives got this.

Some people have made observations - condition is a sign of aging because they have seen most patients detected were in the late forties, but this isn't true as per the veins center san Jose. The reason why the later stage in life is due to you has related to the ailment to progress

and show itself visibly. Anyway, spider vein treatment near me in San Diego is the deal you can put your efforts into.

You Can't Heal Condition, The Veins Usually Reoccur

This is incorrect as once you get cleared of the causative circumstance you will reduce the condition. For instance, if your condition is driven by high blood stress, asking about the way that manages the blood stress will heal the situation. While taking the spider vein treatment in San Diego you should tell about the blood problems you are having.

The same thing affects if the ailment is brought about by hormones. Basically, you need to take care of the root cause. You only need to focus on the hormones and the condition will get corrected. While modern procedures of [varicose vein treatment near me](#) are very effective, recurrence does happen in about 5% of the patient which is very low. In this case, you only need to do some touch-up care.

It happens only in Women

Research studies have shown that varicose is limited to women but that's not the case it can happen to anyone. As per the studies, men are less likely to have this ailment because triggers are not present.

The Condition has no health-related consequences

While doctors say that you don't need to treat anything until it is not showing any symptoms, varicose veins are true expectations they can be harmful without any consequences. This is because the condition is a sign of a medical ailment and can turn into something serious.

For example, the condition is a sign of a venous problem. Over time the damage may become severe resulting in venous leg ulcers and other open wounds.

Moral of the story

These are clarified facts about the varicose veins. Always remember this condition is a serious medical concern and you need to get it checked by the doctor without any delay. The cool thing is that you don't require to pay thousands of bucks to get it treated. Consultation with a vein doctor and some home remedies can do wonders.